

MERLIN Project's Innovative Approach to Recycling Multilayer Packaging in Europe

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Abstract:

In 2022, Europe collected 32.3 million tonnes of post-consumer plastic waste, but only 37.8% of plastic packaging was recycled, while 44.9% was incinerated and 17.3% was landfilled¹. This situation is still far from the objective of recycling 55% of plastic in 2030, as established in the European Plastics Strategy² and Directive (European Union, EU) 2018/852 on Packaging and Packaging Waste³. The demand for multilayer packaging poses a challenge in sorting plants, as current technologies can only detect the surface layer. Multilayer packaging, comprising incompatible polymer layers bonded with high-strength adhesive, often ends up in landfills or incinerators due to the complexity of separation methods.

Addressing this issue, the MERLIN project focuses on identifying and recycling multilayer rigid, non-metalized flexible, and metalized flexible packaging. It tailors a specific recovery process for each type, separating and recycling plastic fractions and repolymerizing them for packaging demonstrators. The challenge lies in improving sorting and recycling processes for these plastics, particularly from post-consumer sources.

Delamination, the process of separating layers, varies based on packaging nature. For non-metalized films, MERLIN employs green solvent-based processes. Hansen solubility parameters are studied to reduce interlayer interaction, achieving delamination through solvents under supercritical conditions (e.g., CO₂) combined with green solvents. After these processes, different polyester and polyolefin fractions are separated and temporarily recovered.

In essence, MERLIN aims to enhance recycling rates for post-consumer plastic waste, especially multilayer packaging, by developing tailored recovery processes and addressing challenges in delamination. The project aligns with European directives, striving to meet recycling targets and reduce the environmental impact of plastic waste.

Keywords: delamination, plastics, multilayer, packaging, recycling, waste, supercritical CO₂, co-solvents.

1 Introduction

Plastics, including commonly used types such as polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and others, have become ubiquitous in various sectors of society. The global production of plastics has surged over the years, with approximately 322 million tonnes manufactured in 2015 alone⁴. However, a significant challenge lies in managing plastic waste, with a portion being recycled, while a considerable amount ends up in landfills or incineration facilities.

Multilayer films, a notable application of plastics, rely on adhesives to bond different layers together. Commonly used adhesives include acrylics and polyurethanes, each with distinct characteristics and suitability for specific applications. Acrylic adhesives offer strong bonding properties and resistance to environmental factors, while polyurethane adhesives provide flexibility and durability.

Plastics find diverse applications across sectors, depending on the type of polymer and their barrier properties. For instance, low-density polyethylene (LDPE) and high-density polyethylene (HDPE) are commonly used in packaging due to their barrier properties against moisture and gases like oxygen. The production process, such as extrusion or injection moulding, also plays a crucial role in determining the final application of plastics, whether it be for packaging, construction, or agricultural purposes.

Addressing the challenge of tackling the intricate structure of multilayer packaging, various possibilities emerge for developing effective delamination processes. One promising option is the application of mechanical methods such as shredding and blade milling, which can fragment the packaging into individual layers. Alternatively, chemical approaches involving solvent-based delamination techniques offer potential solutions. These methods

involve selectively dissolving specific components or layers using solvents or solvent blends, enabling the separation of materials for recycling or recovery purposes.

In light of the growing concerns surrounding plastic waste management and the pressing need for sustainable solutions, the main objective of this research is to develop an innovative delamination process tailored for various fractions, particularly focusing on polyesters and polyolefins. This process will harness the power of green solvents, such as CO₂ in supercritical conditions, supplemented with co-solvents, to selectively dissolve either the adhesive(s) between layers or target specific layer(s) within the structure. By strategically dismantling multilayer films, this approach aims to facilitate efficient recycling and recovery of valuable materials while minimizing environmental impact.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

To facilitate the development and scaling of delamination processes for multilayer packaging, samples were obtained from typical multilayer packaging waste used in the preservation of frozen food. These samples represent a standard composition found in such packaging, comprising layers of various materials designed to provide insulation and protect frozen products. To be realistic about the delamination of multimaterial packaging in non-aluminised material, a study of the materials used was carried out by creating a library of multilayer materials. These references were classified according to the combination of their layers. Some of these samples are shown in Figure 1.

The selection of these samples ensures that delamination techniques are applicable to real-world scenarios, thereby increasing the practical relevance of research outcomes.

Figure 1: Examples of the selected samples for the delamination process.

2.2 Analytical methods

The physico-chemical properties of the packaging waste under study were assessed using several techniques. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) facilitated qualitative analysis of the material's structure by identifying peaks in the spectrum corresponding to functional groups and bonds. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) measured heat flux differences to determine parameters like melting and crystallization temperatures and enthalpies, as well as the degree of crystallinity. Optical microscopy provided detailed images, especially effective with samples rich in birefringent materials, aiding in the understanding of structural changes within the material. These techniques collectively offer valuable insights into the composition and behaviour of the packaging waste, essential for developing effective delamination processes.

2.3 Supercritical CO₂ plant

The s-CO₂ plant utilized in this project comprises several essential components, as shown in Figure 2. Firstly, the supply system includes a cryogenic circuit with a CO₂ inlet from a bottle, fed into a heat exchanger cooled to -10°C by a chiller. A high-pressure diaphragm pump, capable of operating up to pressures of 250 bar and temperatures of -10°C, facilitates the circulation of liquid CO₂. The pump is controlled by a variable frequency drive for regulation. An additional strategy was employed to augment delamination efficiency. A co-solvent dosing system is integrated to complement the use of s-CO₂. This system enables the simultaneous utilization of both s-CO₂ and a selected co-solvent, capitalizing on their synergistic effects to enhance the overall delamination process.

Secondly, the delamination reactor functions as a piston flow reactor (PFR), with an internal volume of 1 L and maximum operating pressure and temperature of 250 bar and 150°C respectively. It incorporates temperature control, pressure sensors, safety valves, and other essential features to ensure safe and efficient operation.

Lastly, the recovery system includes a pressure regulator connected to the reactor lid for CO₂ evacuation, a cyclone separator with temperature and pressure control, and a condensate separator for condensate evacuation. Safety measures such as manual back pressure regulators and valves are integrated into the system to regulate pressure effectively. Overall, these components work together to facilitate the delamination process in a controlled and efficient manner.

Figure 2: Schematic of the s-CO₂ plant.

2.4 Hansen solubility parameters

Hansen Solubility Parameters (HSP) have emerged as a valuable tool for understanding solubility-related issues in various applications. In the context of developing the delamination process, the HSP provide a comprehensive framework for understanding solubility-related phenomena by quantifying the interactions between solvents and solutes. These parameters consist of three components: dispersion forces (δ_d), polar forces (δ_p), and hydrogen bonding forces (δ_h). By characterizing these forces, HSP offer valuable insights into the compatibility between different substances and help predict their solubility behaviour.

Dispersion forces (δ_d) represent the Van der Waals interactions between molecules, primarily influenced by the size and shape of the molecules involved. Polar forces (δ_p) arise from permanent dipoles within molecules, reflecting their polarity and ability to interact with other polar molecules. Hydrogen bonding forces (δ_h) capture the strength of hydrogen bonds between molecules, which play a crucial role in determining solubility, especially for compounds capable of forming hydrogen bonds.

In the context of delamination processes, such as those involving s-CO₂ for separating polymer layers in multilayer films, understanding the HSP of both the solvent and the polymer layers is essential. By comparing the HSP of s-CO₂ with those of the polymers used in the multilayer films, researchers can identify solvents with HSP values that closely match those of the polymer layers. This matching ensures optimal solubility and interaction between the solvent and the polymer, facilitating effective delamination. The representation of the HSP space is illustrated in Figure 3.

Moreover, HSP analysis enables the selection of co-solvents or additives that can enhance the delamination process by complementing the solubility characteristics of s-CO₂. By identifying solvents or additives with HSP values that complement or adjust the overall HSP profile of the solvent system, researchers can tailor the solvent mixture to achieve desired delamination outcomes.

Figure 3: Representation of Hansen Solubility Parameters space⁵.

3 Main results

3.1 Characterization of samples

The samples received are frozen food related packaging. This type of flexible packaging is non-aluminised and usually has a similar layer structure. The samples received were characterised to conduct a market study and obtain results that could be scaled to reality, as shown as an example in Figure 4. 11 of these samples were selected for having common materials formed from an outer PET and an inner PE layer.

To perform this characterization, a Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) test was carried out. This test shows the different melting points present in a material sample. These points are characteristic of the materials it contains and although with some variation allowed, they are an excellent reflection of the composition of each sample. With this test the different materials to which the sample belongs are obtained.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) tests were also carried out. These tests obtain the characteristic spectroscopy of each material on each surface, which makes it possible to differentiate between the material on the outer face and that on the inner face. In addition, some samples were subjected to cross-sectional microscopic analysis. This test allows to see the different layers that compose the multilayer material, to know their thicknesses and the number of layers they have.

The results obtained showed that in the packaging market there is a predominance of multilayer PET/PE packaging with a thin layer of adhesive. These samples have a higher PE content to the detriment of PET.

Figure 4: Characterization of one sample by: a) Differential Scanning Calorimetry, b) Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, and c) cross-sectional microscopic analysis.

3.2 Evaluation of Hansen solubility parameters

Film adhesives commonly used in the industry were evaluated for their solubility in different solvents, with Morchem XPS 2472 + CS952 adhesive⁶ showing promising results and chosen for further assessment. In HSP space, solvents are represented as points in a three-dimensional space based on their δ_d , δ_p , and δ_h values. While perfect HSP matches are not necessary for solubility, characteristic differences in these parameters determine the compatibility radius within the HSP sphere. The sphere obtained for the Morchem XPS 2472 + CS952 adhesive, shown in Figure 5, was made using 12 different solvents. This comprehensive approach facilitates the selection of effective solvents for the delamination process, enhancing its efficiency and effectiveness.

The obtained HSP for the Morchem XPS 2472 + CS952 adhesive were 18.09 for dispersion (δ_d), 8.63 for polarity (δ_p), and 5.29 for hydrogen bonding (δ_h). These parameters have been instrumental in determining which solvents are best suited for delaminating the evaluated adhesives, guiding the selection process for optimal solvent candidates.

Figure 5: Sphere obtained with Morchem XPS 2472 + CS952 adhesive.

3.3 Effect of main operational conditions

A design of experiments (DoE) was carried out to explore the interaction between various process parameters, including time, temperature, pressure, and CO₂ ratio. Through this DoE, the delamination process parameters were optimized to encompass a broad range of conditions, maximizing the delamination of flexible multilayer structures with a versatile approach at the laboratory scale. It was observed that the structure of the materials directly influenced the efficiency of the delamination process, with certain operating conditions proving more effective for certain structures compared to others, particularly when different types of adhesives or barrier coatings were employed.

In a s-CO₂ plant, time, pressure, and temperature play critical roles, as shown in Figure 6. Exposure time affects process efficiency and stability, while pressure impacts CO₂ solubility and density, requiring careful balancing to mitigate risks. Temperature influences solubility and extraction selectivity. Therefore, a meticulous approach to adjusting these factors is paramount for optimizing efficiency and product quality, especially in industrial applications like extraction and power generation.

Figure 6: Delamination results obtained in different film samples tested.

3.4 Optimisation of s-CO₂ conditions

Extensive efforts have been dedicated to refining the conditions for the supercritical CO₂ delamination process of multilayer films. Through systematic optimisation, a set of optimal parameters has been identified, including a pressure within the range of 150-200 bar, temperature in the range of 60-100°C, and regulation of the CO₂ flow rate between 30-50 mL/min.

This precise calibration of pressure, temperature, and CO₂ ratio has proven instrumental in achieving superior results in the delamination process, ultimately enhancing overall performance and quality in the treatment of multilayer films. It is remarkable to add that none of the samples completely delaminated; only bubbles were observed at the interface.

3.5 Optimisation of use of co-solvents

The optimisation of cosolvents involved exploring their effectiveness in promoting layer separation during the delamination process. Three process aids were evaluated: cosolvents, flow rates, and perforations. The performance was assessed by assigning a score based on the degree of delamination of each of the 11 samples: no delamination 0, bubble generation 1, partial delamination 2, complete delamination 3.

The optimized conditions are used to prepare materials for the project. The optimized conditions resulted in a total of 3 samples with complete delamination, 5 with bubble generation, and 3 with no delamination out of a total of 11 samples evaluated. This translates to a process efficiency of 72.7%.

4 Conclusions

It can be concluded that one of the main problems in the delamination of non-aluminised multilayer material is the heterogeneity of the materials used, especially in relation to the adhesive and its multiple configurations. In this context the operation of the s-CO₂ plant consisting of the feed system, the delamination reactor and the recovery system was satisfactory.

In the pursuit of refining the s-CO₂ delamination process for multilayer films, extensive efforts have led to the identification of optimal conditions. These include maintaining a pressure between 150-200 bar, temperature ranging from 60-100°C, and regulating CO₂ flow rate between 30-50 mL/min. This calibration has been pivotal in enhancing the delamination process, resulting in improved performance and quality.

Furthermore, the optimisation of cosolvents has played a crucial role in facilitating layer separation. Through the evaluation of various process aids, including cosolvents, flow rates, and perforations, a scoring system was employed to assess performance. The optimized conditions yielded promising results, with a process efficiency of 72.7%.

Overall, the systematic optimisation of both s-CO₂ conditions and the use of cosolvents has significantly contributed to advancing the delamination process for multilayer films, showcasing promising prospects for further enhancements in efficiency and quality. These findings underscore the importance of carefully calibrating operational parameters to achieve consistent and favourable delamination outcomes.

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